

EFFECTS OF HYGROTHERMAL ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF ADVANCED FIBRE HYBRID COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Hygrothermal effects on neat resin and advanced composites with simple (Carbon, Kevlar) and hybrid (Carbon/Kevlar) fibres were studied before and after exposure to water immersion at 343 K for 800 hours. The degradation in the mechanical properties and the change in failure process were determined. A torsional test rig was used to determine the hygrothermal effects on neat resin. Acoustic emission and SEM techniques were employed to study the failure process. The experimental investigations revealed a significant change in the failure process in the composites in addition to the degradation in the mechanical properties, due to hygrothermal effects.

INTRODUCTION

Advanced composite materials provide lot of advantages for aircraft and marine structural applications, in terms of its superior strength and stiffness properties. However the moisture absorption by the matrix and the permeable fibres in a composite, when exposed to hot humid environment, causes considerable concern for the designers and engineers. Extensive work has been carried out to understand the hygrothermal effects on the degradation of strength and stiffness properties of composites [1,2]. In this paper the hygrothermal effects on failure process in addition to the degradation of mechanical properties of neat resin both in thick (1.5 mm to 2 mm) and thin film (0.1 mm to 1.0 mm) and carbon, kevlar and carbon/kevlar hybrid fibre composites all in an Epoxy matrix, are presented. Acoustic emission and SEM methods are adopted to study the change in failure process.

EXPERIMENTAL

Carbon, kevlar and carbon/kevlar hybrid composite laminates were fabricated using an autoclave moulding technique. Tensile, Interlaminar Shear Strength and Shear Modulus test specimens were cut from the laminates as per ASTM standards. The specimens were then edge coated and immersed in water maintained at 343 K for 900 hours to attain saturation [3]. The specimens were then subjected to static tests by using an Instran Testing Machine. The strength (F_L , F_T , F_{LT}) and stiffness (E_L , E_T , μ_{LT} and G_{LT}) were determined, before and after exposure to environment. The degradation in the mechanical properties are shown in Table-1.

Acoustic Emission Studies: The static tests were accompanied by an online Acoustic emission monitoring during the load

cycle. AE cumulative counts have been measured as a function of stress in both dry and hygrothermally conditioned test specimens. The AE cumulative counts vs stress plots for carbon, kevlar and carbon/kevlar hybrid composites are presented in Fig.1.

SEM Studies: In order to further understand the effects of hygrothermal on the failure process, SEM studies were carried out on the fractured specimens before and after exposure to environment. A scanning electron microscope JSM-35 was used for studying the fracture morphology.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

It is seen from table-1 that the strength and modulus of neat resin, both bulk and thin film has significant degradation due to the hygrothermal effects. The degradation in composites with permeable fibres (Kevlar) was found to be more than the impermeable fibre composites. From Fig.1, a significant change in AE counts Vs. stress plots are seen for carbon, kevlar, carbon/Kevlar hybrid composites, before and after exposure to environment. In the case of exposed specimens, the AE activity was seen right from the beginning to the end of the load cycle, indicating a gradual failure. Also the number of counts in exposed specimen was found to be more than the unexposed ones. This is due to the degradation of the matrix and the fibre matrix interface causing plastisization of matrix and fibre slipping in addition to matrix crazing, delamination etc. The effect was predominant in the kevlar and kevlar/carbon hybrid composites and insignificant in the CFRP composites. The SEM photographs of CFRP Composites before and after exposure of magnification 500 and 1000, shown in Fig.2 and 3 respectively, clearly show the fibre slippage. Similar effect was seen in KFRP and K/C FRP composites. In addition to this, surface degradation, absence of matrix on the fibres and enlargement of voids are noticed on the exposed specimen.

CONCLUSION

Hygrothermal effects cause significant change in the failure process of neat resin and the composites with permeable and impermeable fibres in addition to the degradation of the mechanical properties. The matrix dominated properties are greatly affected. AE studies revealed a significant change in the failure processes from gradual to brittle and catastrophic. SEM analysis revealed predominant fibre slippage, matrix fibre degradation and swelling of composites.

REFERENCES

1. Springer G.S., Ed., Environmental Effects on Composite Materials vol.1-3, Technomic Publishing Company, 1981, 1984 & 1987.
2. Kretsis G., A Review of the Tensile, compressive, flexural and shear properties of Hybrid fibre reinforced plastics, Jr.Composites, Vol.1, January 1987.
3. Gopalan R., Dattaguru B., Murthy M.V.V., and Rao R.M.V.G.K., Diffusion studies on advance fibre hybrid composites, Jr. Reinforced plastics and composites, Vol.14, January 1986.

Table 1 Hygrothermal effects on mechanical properties of Advanced Composites.

MATERIAL SYSTEM.	TENSILE STRENGTH (MPa)		YOUNGS MODULUS (MPa)		SHEAR MODULUS (MPa)		ILSS (MPa)	
	Unexp.	Exp.	Unexp.	Exp.	Unexp.	Exp.	Unexp.	Exp.
NEAT RESIN								
Bulk	62.1	41.5	2900.0	1595.0	2367.6	1258.7	11.5	8.8
Thin	-	-	-	-	3100.0	2500.0	39.7	15.0
GFRP	321.0	277.0	26685.0	22656.0	5880.0	5090.0	44.7	36.9
CFRP	768.4	670.0	78430.0	71420.0	5776.0	4587.0	46.6	38.2
KFRP	684.4	602.0	51400.0	34700.0	4911.0	3324.7	34.5	26.6
C/KFRP	1070.0	996.8	119170.0	109090.0	5340.0	4272.0	38.1	30.5

FIG. 1 CUMULATIVE COUNTS VS STRESS FOR CARBON, KEVLAR AND CARBON/KEVLAR COMPOSITES.

FIG. 2 FRACTURE SURFACE MORPHOLOGY SHOWING A GOOD FIBRE MATRIX INTERFACE OF CFRP SPECIMEN BEFORE EXPOSURE.

FIG. 3 FRACTURE SURFACE MORPHOLOGY OF CFRP SPECIMEN AFTER EXPOSURE SHOWING THE MATRIX DEGRADATION AND FIBRE SLIPPING.